

1 **Many diets for many people: planetary health diets and their health and**
2 **environmental impacts at global, regional, national, and demographic levels**

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12 **Abstract**

13

14 Without dietary changes towards healthier and more sustainable diets, there is little chance
15 of addressing the growing burden of non-communicable diseases, avoiding dangerous levels
16 of climate change, and staying within key planetary boundaries that define a safe operating
17 space for humanity. Global reference values for healthy and sustainable eating exist, but
18 consistent adaptations to local contexts are limited, which impacts food-related planning and
19 decision-making. Here we develop a diverse set of “planetary health diets” that are adapted
20 to the nutritional needs and preferences of populations at global, regional, national, and
21 demographic levels. The set includes distinct dietary patterns (flexitarian, pescatarian,
22 vegetarian, vegan) that differ across countries, age groups, and sexes. Using impact
23 assessments, we show that adoption of these diets would be associated with substantial
24 improvements in nutritional adequacy and simultaneous reductions in diet-related mortality
25 and environmental resource demand, in each case across a wide range of regional and
26 demographic scales. Our findings also indicate large differences to current diets, suggesting
27 the need for dedicated initiatives and support for dietary change. We integrated the
28 estimates of food intake and the associated impacts into interactive analysis tools to facilitate
29 dietary planning and decision-making across dietary preferences at regional and
30 demographic levels.

31 **Introduction**

32

33 The health and environmental challenges that are posed by unhealthy and unsustainable
34 diets, and the food system underpinning those, have emerged as key public and planetary
35 health concerns ^{1,2}. Unhealthy diets are a leading risk factor for non-communicable diseases
36 (NCDs), responsible for one in five deaths globally ^{3,4}. The food systems producing those
37 diets are major drivers of environmental resource use and pollution, including climate
38 change, land use and biodiversity loss, and water use and pollution ^{2,5,6}. Without dietary
39 changes towards healthier and more sustainable diets, there is little chance of addressing
40 the growing burden of NCDs, avoiding dangerous levels of climate change, and staying
41 within key planetary boundaries that define a safe operating space for humanity ⁷.

42

43 Despite general agreement on the importance of dietary change, a clear and comprehensive
44 description is lacking of how healthy and sustainable diets can look like at various scales,
45 including at country and population levels ². Although dietary guidelines exist for some
46 countries, many of them have been found to be inconsistent with global health and
47 environmental targets, often due to vague recommendations for foods important for public
48 and planetary health ⁸. In response, a set of global recommendations for a “planetary health
49 diet” has been developed to be both healthy and sustainable ², but their global scope has
50 raised issues of adaptability to national circumstances and preferences, as well as their
51 nutritional suitability for all segments of society ⁹, especially as their main illustration was for
52 the energy needs of a specific population group ².

53

54 Here we develop a diverse and nutritionally balanced set of options of healthy and
55 sustainable dietary patterns for all countries and population groups within those. Our
56 analysis – undertaken as part of the (second) EAT-Lancet Commission on Healthy,
57 Sustainable, and Just Food Systems ¹⁰ – expands the planetary health diet into four distinct
58 and compatible dietary patterns to provide additional choice whilst combining nutritional

59 adequacy at the population level with environmental sustainability at the global level. The
60 dietary patterns include flexitarian diets with low to moderate amounts of animal source
61 foods, pescatarian diets which include seafood but no other meat, vegetarian diets which
62 include dairy and eggs but no meat or fish, and vegan diets which do not include any animal
63 source foods. For each dietary pattern, we developed specific dietary options that are
64 adapted to the demographic (age and sex) groups within each country based on nutritional
65 needs and dietary preferences.

66

67 To further characterise the dietary patterns and to inform decision making on dietary change,
68 we estimated the health and environmental impacts of adopting the different dietary patterns
69 across scales. We quantified impacts on nutritional adequacy, dietary risks and mortality, and
70 environmental resource use and pollution. Our analysis advances the characterisation of
71 healthy and sustainable diets by substantially expanding the level of regional, demographic,
72 and dietary detail and by improving methods for assessing their impacts. This includes using
73 a biophysically grounded proxy for food intake in developing the dietary patterns, estimating
74 the nutritional adequacy of populations across regions and demographic groups, quantifying
75 the burden of dietary risks related to both composition and overall intake, and tracking food-
76 related environmental impacts consistently across the food system and environmental
77 domains.

78

79 To ease the use of our analysis in the planning of dietary policies and food-related initiatives
80 by various actors and at different scales, we compiled a set of supplementary datafiles that
81 contain the full details and estimated impacts of all dietary patterns for each country (184 in
82 total) and population group (up to 22 age groups, 5 age classes, and 2 sexes). The
83 assessment tools, data, and results will be also made available as part of the World Health
84 Organization's Dietary Impact Assessment (DIA) model ¹¹, version 2.0.

85

86 **Healthy and sustainable dietary patterns**

87

88 We based the development of healthy and sustainable dietary patterns on a comprehensive
89 review of the scientific evidence on healthy eating conducted as part of the first and second
90 EAT-Lancet Commissions on Healthy Diets from Sustainable and Just Food Systems ^{2,10}.

91 Reference values identified to be in line with optimal health outcomes in adults include a
92 balanced energy intake and at least five servings of vegetables and fruits per day, one to two
93 servings of legumes and nuts per day each, a preference for whole grains over refined
94 grains, and for oils high in unsaturated fatty acids over those high in saturated fats and
95 animal fats, up to one serving of red meat per week, two servings of poultry, fish, and eggs
96 per week each, and one serving of dairy and starchy roots per day each. The reference
97 values are compatible with several dietary patterns, including flexitarian diets with low to
98 moderate levels of animal source foods, pescatarian diets which include seafood but no
99 other meat, vegetarian diets which include dairy and eggs but no meat or fish, and vegan
100 diets which do not include any animal source foods.

101

102 Starting with flexitarian diets, we developed population-specific diets by following several
103 steps (*Methods*). First, we implemented the reference values as ceilings and floors (Fig 1A),
104 which ensured that populations whose intake already fulfilled the recommendations were not
105 penalised from reductions in encouraged foods or increases in discouraged ones. For a
106 sensitivity analysis, we also implemented the reference values without adjustment. Second,
107 we further regionalised the diets by preserving the dietary preferences within general food
108 groups, e.g. of the types of grains, red meat, fish, and fruits. Third, we adjusted first grain
109 intake and then oil intake to fulfil the recommended energy intake of adults across countries
110 and regions, and we scaled overall food intake to fulfil the recommended energy intake
111 across sexes and age groups (Fig 1B). For a sensitivity analysis, we used only grain intake
112 for balancing energy intake. Fourth, we generated the full set of dietary patterns by replacing
113 either meat (pescatarian), meat and fish (vegetarian), or all animal source foods (vegan) with
114 a mix of fruits, vegetables, and legumes, informed by observed patterns of substitution in

115 specialised dietary patterns ¹². Lastly, we balanced the intake of micronutrients for each
116 population group by adjusting the intake of nutrition-sensitive foods within general food
117 groups (e.g., of green-leafy vegetables and soybeans for iron, and including a small portion
118 of algae for B vitamins ¹³).

119

120 The set of dietary patterns differ across regions and population groups (Fig 2, Fig S3). For
121 example, flexitarian diets in North America contained mostly wheat as grains (70%), beef as
122 red meat (55%), and shellfish as seafood (40%), whereas diets in East Asia contained
123 mostly rice as grain (70%), pork as red meat (70%), and freshwater fish as seafood (40%).
124 Across age groups, the diets (flexitarian and others) of children contained 45% less calories
125 as the population average and consequently less servings of foods (e.g., 3.5 servings of
126 grains per person per day (servings/d) compared to 6), whereas those of adults contained
127 about 10% more calories and foods (e.g., 7 servings/d of grains). Across sexes, the diets of
128 women contained 10% less calories as the average (e.g., 5.5 servings/d of grains), whereas
129 the diets of men contained 10% more calories (e.g., 7 servings/d of grains). Compared to
130 flexitarian diets, pescatarian, vegetarian, and vegan diets contained gradually lower amounts
131 of animal source foods, but also gradually more fruits and vegetables (+10-30%, or 6.5-8
132 servings/d compared to 6) and more legumes (+10-50%, or up to 2 servings/d compared to
133 1.5).

134

135 **Difference to current intake**

136

137 The dietary patterns differ substantially from current dietary intake (Fig 2, Fig S6). On
138 average, they contain larger amounts of fruits (+40-80% across the dietary patterns, ranging
139 from flexitarian diets to vegan ones), vegetables (+70-120%), legumes (+230-380%), nuts
140 and seeds (+270%), and vegetable oils (+75%), and lower amounts of beef and lamb (-70-
141 100%), pork (-80-100%), poultry (-35-100%), dairy (-40-100%), eggs (-55-100%), fish (-35-
142 100%), oils high in saturated fat (-45%), sugar (-50%), roots (-70%), and grains (-20%). The

143 changes expressed in servings ranged from less than 0.5 servings/d on average for animal
144 source foods to 2-3 for vegetables, vegetable oils, and sugar (Figs S4-S5).

145

146 To describe the degree of dietary change across regions and demographic groups, we
147 calculated the overall percentage change in the intake of all encouraged foods with minimum
148 intake targets and that of all to-be-limited foods with maximum targets. Across regions and
149 for the example of flexitarian diets (Figs S7-S8), the overall percentage change in
150 encouraged foods ranged from 45% in East Asia (primarily driven by whole grains) to 145%
151 in Sub-Saharan Africa (driven by both vegetables and whole grains). The change in to-be-
152 limited foods ranged from 30% in South Asia (driven by refined grains) to 50% in North
153 America (driven by milk). Across demographic groups, the absolute changes in intake were
154 generally larger in groups with higher energy needs such as men and adults, whereas the
155 proportional changes were often larger in groups with lower energy needs such as children.

156

157 **Nutritional impacts**

158

159 The dietary patterns are associated with improvements in nutritional balances (Fig 3A, Fig
160 S9). On average, they increased mineral intake, including calcium (+10-30%), iron (+40-
161 70%), and zinc (+10-20%), in each case primarily driven by more vegetables and legumes.
162 They also increased the intake of most vitamins, including vitamin C (+70-110%) and vitamin
163 A (+230-290%), again driven by vegetables; and vitamin B12 (+110-180%), driven by algae
164 rich in B12 (with some varieties of tempeh, i.e., fermented soybeans as another plant-based
165 alternative ¹³). In addition, macronutrient composition improved due to greater intake of
166 protein (+5%), fibre (+70-110%), and poly-unsaturated fatty acids (+90-100%), and lower
167 intake of carbohydrates (-15-25%) and saturated fat (-10-40%).

168

169 By construction, the dietary patterns meet the nutritional requirements of each population
170 group and attained full nutrient adequacy scores across regions, age groups, and sexes

171 (Figs S10-S11). We calculated the adequacy scores by averaging nutrient adequacy ratios
172 (i.e., the ratio between estimated and recommended intake capped at one) of nutrients with
173 recommendations to avoid deficiency (*Methods*). According to our estimates (Fig 3A), the
174 dietary patterns increased average nutrient adequacy by 6% globally, which was driven by
175 improving low intakes of riboflavin, iodine, and iron, followed by vitamins C, A, B12, as well
176 as folate and zinc. Across regions, the average improvements in nutrient adequacy ranged
177 from 4% in East Asia to 12% in Sub-Saharan Africa where current adequacy of vitamin B12
178 is particularly low. Across demographic groups, they ranged from 5% in men to 8% in women
179 who have greater iron needs and current deficiencies, and from 5% in young adults to 8% in
180 senior adults who have greater current deficiencies in vitamin C.

181

182 **Health impacts**

183

184 The dietary patterns are associated with reductions in diet-related disease risk and mortality
185 across regions and population groups (Fig 3B). For our assessment of long-term health
186 impacts, we conducted a comparative risk assessment of diet and weight-related risks based
187 on cause-specific mortality rates and established risk-disease relationships (*Methods*).
188 According to our analysis, the dietary patterns are associated with reductions in mortality of
189 18-20%, corresponding to 10-11 million avoided deaths globally (Fig S12). Most of the
190 reductions in mortality were from coronary heart diseases (45%), followed by cancer (30%),
191 type-2 diabetes (5%), and respiratory disease (5%), with similar contributions from
192 improvements in risks related to dietary composition and risks related overall food intake and
193 energy imbalances that affect weight levels (Fig S13).

194

195 The health impacts differed by dietary pattern, region, and demographic groups (Fig 3B, Fig
196 S14). Across diets, the reductions in mortality ranged from 18% for flexitarian diets to 20% in
197 vegan diets which contained relatively more foods associated with reductions in disease risk
198 (vegetables, fruits, and legumes), and less foods associated with increased risks (red and

199 processed meat). Across regions and for the example of flexitarian diets, the reductions
200 ranged from 10-11% in Sub-Saharan Africa which has a relatively young population and
201 lower incidence of diet-related NCDs to 24-27% in Europe and Central Asia which has an
202 older population and high incidence of NCDs. Across demographic groups, the reductions
203 were similar in women (18-20%) and men (18-19%), by they ranged from 6-7% in young
204 adults to 20-21% in senior adults who have higher mortality rates.

205

206 **Environmental pressures and impacts**

207

208 The dietary patterns are associated with less environmental resource use and pollution (Fig
209 3C, Fig S15). For assessing the environmental impacts, we estimated changes in total food
210 demand associated with the diet scenarios and then paired those for each food commodity
211 with a set of trade-adjusted and regionalised environmental footprints (*Methods*). According
212 to our analysis, the dietary patterns are associated with changes in food demand that would
213 reduce global food-related GHG emissions by 30-50% (5-8 GtCO₂eq), land use by 45-70%
214 (20-35 Mkm²), including cropland use by 2-10% (0.5-1.5 Mkm²), as well as water use by 25-
215 35% (850-1,100 km³), and eutrophication potential by 35-55% (25-40 MtPO₃⁴-eq). The
216 reductions in most domains were primarily driven by less intake and production of animal
217 source foods (Figs S16-S17). As a consequence, the environmental impacts were lowest in
218 the more plant-based dietary patterns.

219

220 To provide an overview of impacts across populations (Fig 3C), we averaged the percentage
221 changes in each domain, weighted by the importance of dietary change for mitigation in that
222 domain (*Methods*)⁷. Across dietary patterns, the weighted reductions in environmental
223 impacts ranged from 35% for flexitarian diets which contain moderate amounts of animal
224 source foods to 50% for vegan diets which contain no animal sourced foods. Across regions
225 and for the example of flexitarian diets, reductions ranged from 10% in South Asia to 50% in
226 both North America and Latin America where diets are relatively high in animal source foods.

227 Across age groups, reductions ranged from 25% in children who have less overall food
228 intake to 40% in senior adults whose diets contain relatively high amounts of animal source
229 foods, especially in low and middle-income countries. Across sexes, reductions were
230 comparable (33-35%) but moderately less in women who have a lower intake of animal
231 source foods and a lower overall food intake than men. The regional and demographic
232 trends for the other dietary patterns were comparable (SI Datafiles).

233

234 **Sensitivity analysis**

235

236 In developing the dietary patterns, we implemented the reference values of healthy intake as
237 ceilings and floors, which ensured that populations whose intake already fulfilled the
238 recommendations were not penalised. However, there are alternative perspectives on
239 adopting the reference values, including allowing increases in discouraged foods (e.g., of
240 meat and dairy) up to the ceiling to not penalise potentially increasing preference for such
241 foods, as well as a strict adherence of both floors and ceilings (especially for flexitarian diets)
242 to provide more distinct variants of dietary patterns. In a sensitivity analysis (Fig 4), we
243 assessed the implications of a strict adherence to the reference values of healthy intake (Fig
244 1A), which also included using grain intake for energy balance. Flexitarian diets with strict
245 adherence contained lower amounts of previously encouraged foods (e.g., 25% less
246 vegetables) and more of previously discouraged foods (e.g., 75% more milk, 55% more
247 poultry and fish, and 25% more red meat). As a result, the environmental benefits decreased
248 by 14%, but the health benefits remained comparable with small reductions (-4%).

249

250 The dietary patterns were developed based on the recommended energy and food intake of
251 populations at current levels of physical activity. However, about a third of all adults and four
252 fifth of adolescents do not meet global health recommendations of engaging in at least
253 moderate levels of physical activity ^{14,15}, something that results in increased disease burden
254 and costs ^{16,17}. Ideally, dietary changes towards healthier and more sustainable dietary

255 patterns would be accompanied by efforts to increase physical activity. In a second
256 sensitivity analysis (Fig 4), we therefore developed diets that accommodate the additional
257 energy needs of meeting the World Health Organization's recommendations on physical
258 activity ¹⁸. On average, an additional energy intake of 100 kcal/d was required in those diets,
259 which could be met by, e.g., increasing the intake of whole grains and vegetable oils by a
260 quarter to half a serving per day each. The changes in intake had no substantial impacts on
261 the health and environment benefits identified previously (+2% and -5% respectively).

262

263 In a final sensitivity analysis (Fig 4), we quantified the implications of adopting dietary
264 recommendations developed for a different population group. We based this analysis on a
265 common misinterpretation of the EAT-Lancet reference values, which were expressed for an
266 energy intake of 2500 kcal/d for illustration. Although this level of intake only corresponds to
267 the energy needs of specific population groups such as middle-aged men or physically
268 active young adults, it has often been used as the target for energy intake of the total
269 population ^{19,20}. Using 2500 kcal/d diets for all population groups increased national energy
270 intake by 20% (400 kcal/d) on average in our sensitivity analysis. In addition, it increased the
271 intake of some encouraged foods such as fruits and nuts by 10-15%, as well as the intake of
272 discouraged foods such as red meat and milk by 45-110%. These changes resulted in about
273 a third less health benefits, primarily due to less reductions in overweight and obesity, as
274 well as a halving of the environmental benefits, primarily due to the higher intake of animal
275 source foods.

276

277 **Discussion**

278

279 Dietary changes towards healthier and more sustainable diets across all regions and
280 population groups are necessary for addressing major health and environmental challenges,
281 including limiting global warming, meeting the Sustainable Development Goals related to
282 environmental resource use and pollution, and tackling the ongoing obesity and NCD

283 pandemics^{1,2,4-6}. Here we developed a set of planetary health diets that are adapted to
284 different regions and demographic groups which can be used to inform dietary transitions
285 across scales and actors. By construction, the dietary patterns are nutritionally adequate and
286 in line with food-related planetary boundaries^{2,7}. Our analysis indicates that their adoption
287 would also be associated with substantial reductions in diet-related disease risk and
288 mortality, and in environmental resource use and pollution, in each case across a wide range
289 of regional and demographic scales.

290

291 Our findings show that there are many diets that are both healthy and sustainable, and that
292 healthy and sustainable diets differ by region and demographic group. Providing dietary
293 options that are tailored to the dietary preferences and nutritional requirements of different
294 population groups can help in devising concrete pathways of dietary change, including in
295 policy planning, civil-society initiatives, business approaches, and personal behaviour
296 change. Explicitly including the variety of healthy and sustainable dietary patterns in such
297 pathways allows for agency in dietary choice which increases the likelihood of adoption²¹.
298 Variety of choice could for example be facilitated by a “common core” approach in which the
299 dietary components common to each dietary pattern (e.g., whole grain, vegetables, legumes,
300 nuts, fruits) are provided as a non-exclusionary default, and foods specific to a dietary
301 pattern become an optional choice in proportion dietary reference values.

302

303 The set of healthy and sustainable diets we developed are also relevant for further research.
304 For example, including the set of dietary patterns in impact assessments can help analyse
305 the range of mitigation options more fully than a focus on one variant, something that is
306 supported by the substantially lower environmental impacts we identified for vegan diets
307 compared to flexitarian ones, at similar health and nutritional benefits. The grounding of the
308 set of diets in the nutritional and energy needs of population groups ensures biophysical
309 consistency when using them in dietary impact assessments. This contrasts with many
310 previous analyses that were based on misapplying the dietary reference values of a specific

311 population group (with energy requirements of 2500 kcal/d) to the whole population ^{19,20}. Our
312 analysis suggests this could have resulted in substantial deviations in quantified impacts. We
313 hope the dietary options we developed will facilitate more biophysically grounded research
314 on health, environmental, and social aspects not covered here ^{22,23}.

315

316 Our findings show that current diets differ substantially from the set of healthy and
317 sustainable dietary patterns developed here. Dietary choices are seldomly made based on
318 the health and environmental considerations that form the basis of our analysis. Instead,
319 they are known to be influenced by the availability, prices, tastes, and habits embodied in
320 both local and global food environments. As such, multi-component approaches would be
321 necessary to encourage and enable dietary changes towards healthier and more sustainable
322 dietary patterns ^{24,25}. They can include informational approaches (e.g., food labelling and
323 reforms of dietary guidelines ⁸), but are thought to also require regulatory approaches,
324 including fiscal incentives (e.g., reform of agricultural subsidies ²⁶ and adjusting the pricing of
325 foods according to their health or environmental impacts ²⁷⁻²⁹), as well as gustatory
326 approaches, including menu and meal reformulations, so that healthy and sustainable
327 dietary options are not only encouraged, but also available, affordable, and desirable.

328

329 Our study advances the literature in several ways but is also subject to caveats. First, by
330 developing dietary scenarios by country and population group, we explicitly accounted for
331 regional and demographic differences in energy needs and food-group recommendations,
332 which goes beyond assessments based on national averages ³⁰. We used a new and
333 improved proxy of dietary intake, but the existing estimates of food intake with global
334 coverage that we used for its construction have large uncertainties. They include
335 misreporting in dietary surveys and outdated data on the amount of nationally available food
336 that is wasted ^{31,32}. We used a triangulation method that normalised food intake to those
337 levels of energy intake that are required to sustain measured levels of body weight, height,
338 and physical activity levels in each population group ³³. Whilst this is an improvement on

339 previous approaches, it comes with its own sources of uncertainty, including those related to
340 anthropometric measures.

341

342 Second, by coupling the construction of dietary scenarios with a nutritional assessment, we
343 ensured that all dietary patterns attained nutritional adequacy in each population group
344 (including in women and children), something previous country-level analyses were not able
345 to demonstrate ³⁰. We improved current methods in nutritional analyses by regionalising
346 nutritional recommendations to the demographic and weight distribution of each population
347 group instead of applying reference weights from high-income countries. In addition, we
348 included complementary food sources of nutrients such as vitamin B12 that are especially
349 relevant in predominantly plant-based dietary patterns. Plant-based sources of bioavailable
350 B12 include certain algae and fermented soybeans (tempeh) ^{13,34}. Algae can be grown and
351 harvested in most coastal regions, and soybeans are a widely traded commodity, but regular
352 intake is limited to East Asia. Targeted regulatory, business, and behavioural initiatives might
353 be needed to increase regular consumption in other regions.

354

355 Third, by including both scale and composition-related risks in our analysis of long-term
356 health, we were able to provide a more comprehensive attribution of the diet-related disease
357 burden than most current assessments ³. Compared to other assessments, we only included
358 non-overlapping and food-based dietary risks, used independently derived risk-disease
359 associations whose quality of evidence in meta-analyses have been graded as moderate to
360 high ³⁵⁻³⁷, and omitted composition-related risk factors that showed high regional variability
361 (e.g., fish) or became non-significant in fully adjusted models (e.g., milk). However, despite
362 our conservative approach to disease attribution, residual confounding with unaccounted risk
363 factors cannot be ruled out in the epidemiological studies that derived the disease-risk
364 associations ³⁸.

365

366 Fourth, by pairing regional environmental footprints with current statistics of the global food
367 system, we were able to provide estimates of the potential environmental impacts of dietary
368 change without making additional economic assumption (e.g., related to prices), which we
369 think are a matter of policy. This complements analyses of existing food system models
370 whose baseline data can be several decades old and who therefore rely on (less certain)
371 economic projections and modelling for their estimates ^{39–41}. These models are based on
372 specific behavioural economic assumptions and have a fixed regional focus which make the
373 estimated supply and demand relationships not representative of other contexts. In contrast,
374 our estimates can be used across scales to scope the dietary option space and related
375 impacts, but our analysis does not resolve potential policies or pathways that would result in
376 those changes. Identifying if and with what combination of measures large-scale dietary
377 change can be achieved is still an active area of research ^{25,42,43}.

378

379 Some businesses and interest groups have been promoting the adoption of meat and milk
380 alternatives as practical solutions for reducing especially the environmental footprints of diets
381 ^{44–46}. However, from environmental, health, and cost perspectives, they generally perform
382 worse than the unprocessed plant-based foods the EAT-Lancet Commissions and other
383 dietary guidelines recommend for regular intake ⁴⁷. We therefore did not include them in our
384 set of diets and the related assessments. However, increasing the uptake of less marketable
385 whole foods will likely require a shift in business approaches away from the promotion of
386 single products towards more service and meal-oriented approaches, and an alignment of
387 policy support, including public and private investments into healthy and sustainable meals
388 and diets. Our analysis implies that this might be worthwhile as the health and environmental
389 benefits of such structural changes in diets would be substantial across all geographical
390 scales and population groups.

391

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515 **Methods**

516

517 ***Development of planetary health diets***

518

519 We constructed the dietary patterns by adjusting current intake to meet minimum and
520 maximum recommended values for healthy eating. Estimates of current intake were derived
521 by combining estimates of food composition from waste-adjusted food availability data ^{48,49}
522 with demographic trends in intake from dietary surveys ⁵⁰, and normalised to estimates of
523 total energy intake required to sustain measured levels of body weight, height, and physical
524 activity ³³. The estimates capture complete diets aggregated into 36 primary foods and 7
525 processed foods for 184 countries, 22 age groups in five-year intervals, and two sexes
526 (Table S1, SI section S1). They are regionally and demographically comparable and follow
527 observed trends in over and underconsumption (Fig 1B). For this study, we aggregated the
528 dietary resolution to 24 food commodities to align with the detail of dietary recommendations,
529 and we summarised the demographic detail to ten groups for presentational purposes (whilst
530 keeping the full detail in our computations).

531

532 The values of recommended intake were based on a comprehensive review of the literature
533 on healthy eating conducted by the EAT-Lancet Commissions on Healthy Diets from
534 Sustainable and Just Food Systems, which is available in the EAT-Lancet reports ^{2,10}. The
535 reference values describe healthy food intake for physically active adults, which can be
536 interpreted as minimum and maximum recommendations that allow for a variety of dietary
537 patterns (Fig 1A). Starting with flexitarian diets, we adjusted current intake amongst adults to
538 meet both minimum and maximum recommendations, without reducing intake if it was above
539 minimum values (e.g., for fruits and vegetables) or increasing intake if it was below
540 maximum values (e.g., for red meat and sugar). We preserved regional preferences of
541 specific types of foods within the general categories of grains, red meat, fish, and fruits by
542 using the current distribution of intake within those categories (Table S1).

543

544 We then adjusted energy intake in adults to those energy requirements that are in line with
545 healthy body weights by changing grain and oil intake (whose recommended values were
546 also initially determined by energy and macronutrient balances). Estimates of healthy body
547 weights by country and population group (Fig 1B) were derived by using predictive equations
548 for estimating energy requirements for healthy body weights that minimise mortality risk at
549 current levels of body heights and physical activity³³. For attaining energy balance, we first
550 adjusted grain intake but switched to oils when grain intake exceeded maximum
551 recommendations (six servings per day, 270 g/d), whilst ensuring oil intake stayed within the
552 range recommended for macronutrient balance (40-80 g/d). We constructed diets for other
553 and more specific age groups (at five-year intervals) by scaling food intake by recommended
554 energy intake in that age group.

555

556 We developed the full set of dietary patterns by substitution. We replaced either meat
557 (pescatarian), meat and fish (vegetarian), or all animal source foods (vegan) with a mix of
558 fruits and vegetables and of legumes and fish (pescatarian diets), or with a mix of fruits and
559 vegetables and legumes (vegetarian and vegan diets). The pattern of substitution was based
560 on dietary recommendations and observed patterns of substitution in specialised dietary
561 patterns¹². The mix of fruits and vegetables constituted one third of replaced calories in
562 each case, and the mix of legumes and fish in pescatarian diets was determined based on
563 increasing fish intake up to its recommended value (Fig 1A) and increasing legumes
564 thereafter.

565

566 In a final adjustment, we balanced the intake of micronutrients for each population group by
567 adjusting the composition of nutrient-rich foods within general food groups (e.g., increasing
568 green-leafy vegetables and soybeans within vegetables and legumes for increasing iron
569 intake), and of adding a plant-based source of vitamin B12. For the latter, we used a small
570 serving of algae with bioavailable B12¹³, but note that other options exist, including certain

571 types of tempeh (i.e., fermented soybeans), a range of fortified foods (e.g., soymilks and
572 nutritional yeast), as well as targeted nutrient supplementation, each associated with
573 different food-system implications.

574

575 For comprehensively describing the set of planetary health diets, we used several metrics of
576 food intake. They included intake in weight (grams per person per day), energy content
577 (kilocalories per person per day), and servings (servings per person per day) which were
578 based on amounts customarily consumed (Fig 1A). We also assessed the sensitivity of
579 impacts on the content and construction of the diets. For the sensitivity analyses, we
580 developed and assessed dietary variants with strict adherence to the reference values (i.e.,
581 without allowing overfulfilling recommendations), and with levels of energy intake that are in
582 line with meeting recommendations for physical activity (instead of using current activity
583 levels).

584

585 ***Nutritional assessment***

586

587 We assessed the nutrient adequacy of the dietary patterns by estimating nutrient intake and
588 requirements by region and population group. For estimating nutrient intake, we paired food
589 intake in the different diets with the nutrient densities of foods. We sourced most nutrient
590 densities from the Global Expanded Nutrient Supply (GENuS) model⁵¹, and supplemented
591 them for nutrients and food groups not comprehensively covered by GENuS (e.g., B12 and
592 phytate) by estimates from the Harvard Nutrient Database and specialised food composition
593 tables⁵². To estimate nutrient requirements, we used a set of harmonised nutrient reference
594 values that specify the average nutrient requirements of populations by age and sex⁵³,
595 paired those with detailed population estimates from the United Nations Population Division
596⁵⁴, and adjusted the specified reference weights to the average body weight of each
597 population group in each country⁵⁵. We accounted for changes in the bioavailability of zinc
598 and iron by using established dependencies with dietary modulators (e.g., phytate)^{56–58}.

599

600 In addition to estimating changes in nutrient intake, we combined the estimates of intake with
601 nutrient requirements to calculate nutrient adequacy scores⁵⁹. For each nutrient with an
602 estimated average requirement (EAR) related to adequacy, we calculated nutrient adequacy
603 ratios by dividing estimated intake by recommended intake capped at one, so that a NAR of
604 one represents full adequacy for a population group on average. We then summed all NARs
605 and divided by the number of deficiency-related nutrients to calculate overall nutrient
606 adequacy scores (mean adequacy ratios). This calculation included 14 out of the 26
607 nutrients we assessed intake of because not all nutrients had requirements established in
608 relation to adequacy (Table S2 and SI section S2). Nutrients without adequacy-related EARs
609 included most macronutrients (carbohydrates, fatty acids, and fibre) except for protein, as
610 well as calcium, copper, magnesium, and pantothenate whose EARs were determined by
611 balance studies and observed intake in high-income countries^{60,61}.

612

613 **Comparative risk assessment**

614

615 We assessed the impacts on dietary risks and mortality of the adopting the dietary patterns
616 by using a comparative risk assessment framework with eight diet and weight-related risk
617 factors and five disease endpoints⁸. For parameterizing the comparative risk assessment,
618 we used data on cause-specific mortality from the Global Burden of Disease project⁶², body
619 weight from the NCD Risk Factor Collaboration⁵⁵, and relative risk estimates that relate
620 change in risk factors to changes in disease mortality from meta-analyses of epidemiological
621 cohort studies (Table S3). We focused on adults aged 20 year or older in our assessment
622 due to low mortality rates of NCDs in younger age groups, and we adjusted the relative risks
623 for attenuation with age based on a pooled analysis of cohort studies focussed on metabolic
624 risk factors in line with other studies⁶³.

625

626 The selection of risk-disease associations was supported by available criteria used to judge
627 the certainty of evidence (Table S4). They were graded as moderate or high with NutriGrade
628 ^{35–37}, and assessed as probable or convincing by the Nutrition and Chronic Diseases Expert
629 Group (NutriCoDe) ⁶⁴, and by the World Cancer Research ⁶⁵. For each risk factor, we
630 constrained the maximum attainable risk reduction to minimal risk exposure values
631 established by NutriCoDe and available meta-analyses (SI section S3). We differentiated
632 between composition and weight-related risks in our main analysis. As weight-related risks
633 are associated with imbalanced energy intake, we also conducted a sensitivity analysis in
634 which we attributed weight-related risks to the over and underconsumption of foods
635 (measured in kcal/d) relative to their dietary reference values (Fig 1A).

636

637 **Environmental assessment**

638

639 For calculating environmental impacts, we first converted the estimates of dietary intake to
640 total food demand, and then paired the demand estimates with a set of trade-adjusted and
641 regionalised environmental footprints. To calculate total food demand, we added estimates of
642 food waste to the estimates of dietary intake, and then multiplied the per-person values by
643 the population in the specific demographic group ⁵⁴. Waste estimates of specific foods were
644 based on estimates of the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) ⁴⁹
645 and harmonised to the difference between total calorie intake (derived from anthropometric
646 measures ³³ as used in our estimates of intake, Table S1) and total calorie demand (as
647 reported by the FAO ⁴⁸). This harmonisation accounts for changes in waste fractions from
648 their initial year of analysis and ensures total food demand in the baseline matches the
649 values reported by the FAO.

650

651 The environmental footprints were obtained from a comprehensive meta-analysis of life
652 cycle assessments (LCAs) of 40 foods produced by 38,700 farms in 119 countries, covering
653 GHG emissions, land use, freshwater use, and soil and water pollution as measured by

654 eutrophication potential. The LCAs were standardised by harmonising system boundaries
655 (from inputs to retail) and gap-filling missing steps along the supply chain, which made use
656 of auxiliary estimates (e.g., of post-farm processes) and dedicated process-based models
657 (e.g., of nitrate leaching). FAO data on food production and yields were used to scale and
658 regionalise estimates ⁴⁸, and FAO data on trade were used to derive consumption-based
659 footprints by commodity and region (Table S5, SI section S4).

660

661 In addition to reporting changes in environmental impacts for each domain, we also
662 calculated an overall indicator of food-related environmental impacts. Because the
663 importance of diets and dietary changes for reducing environmental impacts varies for each
664 domain, we used a weighing scheme that accounts for that, with weights assigned based on
665 the needed contribution of dietary changes for staying within food-related environmental
666 limits (or planetary boundaries) while also considering contributions from other food-system
667 measures, including changes in technologies and management practices, food loss and
668 waste, and socio-economic development (Fig S1) ⁷. This meant weighing the changes in
669 GHG emissions relatively more (46%) than changes in eutrophication potential (30%), and
670 land and water use (12% each) (SI section S4). Using simple averages resulted in the same
671 ordering across dietary patterns, regions, and demographic groups, and we included those
672 and the detailed set of estimated impacts in the SI Datafiles.

673

674 **Data Availability**

675 All results produced in this study will be made available as Supplementary Datafiles and
676 uploaded to a public repository.

677

678 **Code availability**

679 The code used in this study will be made available on GitHub and as part of the second
680 version of the World Health Organization's Dietary Impact Assessment (DIA) model ¹¹.

681

682 **Methods references**

683

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744

745 **Contributions**

746 MSp designed the study, conducted the analysis, and wrote the manuscript. All authors
747 provided inputs to the analysis, commented on the manuscript, and approved the
748 submission.

749

750 **Competing interests**

751 The authors declare no competing interests.

752

753 **Additional Information**

754 Supplementary Information and Datafiles are available for this paper. Correspondence and
755 requests for materials should be addressed to Marco Springmann
756 (marco.springmann@ucl.ac.uk or marco.springmann@ouce.ox.ac.uk).

757

758 **Main display items**

759

760 **Fig 1. Main aspects for developing planetary health diets by region and demographic**

761 **group.** The aspects include the planetary health reference values for healthy eating

762 expressed as minimum and maximum targets for dietary intake (shown for adults, **A**),

763 estimates of current dietary intake (shown by country, **B**), and estimates of recommended

764 energy intake (also shown by country, **C**).

Food group	Recommended intake			
	More than		Less than	
	grams per day	servings per day	grams per day	servings per day
Whole grains	135	3	270	6
Vegetable oils	40	3	80	5
Vegetables	300	3		
Fruits	200	2		
Legumes	75	1.5		
Nuts&Seeds	50	2		
Roots			50	1/2
Sugar			30	4
Sat-fat oils			5	1/3
Animal fats			5	1/3
Red meat			15	1/7
Poultry			30	2/7
Fish			30	2/7
Eggs			15	2/7
Milk			250	1

Notes: Dairy is expressed as milk equivalents. Sat-fat oils include oils with high saturated-fat content (e.g., palm and coconut oils). Red meat includes beef, lamb, and pork.

Serving sizes: 45 g for grains, 100 g for roots, vegetables, and fruits, 50 g for legumes, 25 g for nuts, 15 g for oils, 8 g for sugar, 100 g for red meat, poultry, and fish, 50 g for eggs, 250 g for milk

765

766 **Fig 2. Variation in planetary health diets.** Planetary health diets vary across dietary
 767 patterns, regions, and demographic scales (A), in each case with substantial differences to
 768 current intake (B). Food intake in the different diets is expressed in kilocalories per person
 769 per day (kcal/d) and for primary commodities. Intake expressed in other measures (grams
 770 and servings) and for processed foods are reported in the Supplementary Information (Figs
 771 S3-S5). Although total grain intake decreases in most planetary health diets, whole grain
 772 intake increases (Figs S5-S6). The variation across regions, age groups, and sexes are
 773 shown for the example of flexitarian diets. The SI Datafiles contain the complete set of
 774 planetary health diets by dietary pattern, country, and demographic group.

775

776 **Fig 3. Impact assessment of adopting planetary health diets across scales.** The
 777 assessments quantify changes in nutritional adequacy (A), mortality from diet-related
 778 diseases (B), and environmental resource use and pollution (C). The changes denote overall
 779 percentage changes compared to current impacts, and they include proportional
 780 contributions from relevant subcomponents, including nutrients (A), diseases (B), and
 781 environmental indicators (C). The variation across regions, age groups, and sexes are
 782 shown for the example of flexitarian diets. The SI Datafiles contain the complete set of
 783 planetary health diets by dietary pattern, country, and demographic group.

784

785 **Fig 4. Sensitivity analysis of developing planetary health diets.** The sensitivity analysis
 786 compares four ways of developing flexitarian dietary patterns (A) and the associated impacts
 787 on mortality by risk factor (B) and environmental resource demand by food group (C). They
 788 include the main variant which regionalises dietary recommendations without penalising
 789 greater than recommended intake of encouraged foods and lower than recommended intake
 790 of to-be-limited foods (*main*), a static variant with strict adherence to the dietary reference
 791 values (*static*), a variant that is regionalised as the main and adapted to the energy
 792 requirements of populations that meet recommended levels of physical activity (*active*), and
 793 a variant that includes static adherence to the reference values and illustrates the impacts of
 794 misapplying the energy requirements of one population group with energy requirements of
 795 2500 kcal/d to all other groups (*adult*). The sensitivity analysis for other dietary patterns
 796 shows similar trends as flexitarian diets (Fig S19).

797

798

799 **Many diets for many people: planetary health diets**
800 **and their health and environmental impacts at global, regional,**
801 **national, and demographic levels**

802

803 **Supplementary Information**

804

805

806 **Table of Contents**

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813

814

815

816 **S1 Estimates of dietary intake**

817

818 We used global estimates of food intake that are differentiated by country and demographic
819 group within countries ¹. They combine estimates of dietary composition from waste-adjusted
820 food availability estimates sourced from the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United
821 Nations ^{2,3} with demographic trends in intake from dietary surveys sourced from the Global
822 Dietary Database ⁴, normalised to estimates of energy intake required to sustain measured
823 levels of body weight, height, and physical activity ⁵. The latter were derived by applying
824 predictive equations for estimating energy requirements ⁶ (developed based on a global
825 dataset of doubly labelled water studies) to global estimates of body weight, height, and
826 physical activity with country-level and demographic detail ⁷⁻¹⁰. Table S1 provides an
827 overview of the estimates of food intake.

828

829 The estimates of food intake address key shortcomings of existing proxies ^{11,12}. Estimates of
830 food availability capture the composition of food demand, but they are known to
831 overestimate actual intake when not carefully adjusted for food waste ^{13,14}. In contrast,
832 dietary surveys are the only source for inferring demographic variation in intake, but they are
833 prone to substantial underreporting in total intake ¹⁵⁻¹⁹, and existing global databases tend to
834 focus on specific dietary components (e.g., fruits and vegetables, whole and refined grains,
835 and red and processed meat) without capturing complete diets ^{4,20}. Combining information
836 from both sources and adjusting them to estimates of energy intake that are in line with
837 anthropometric measures ensures that the estimates of food intake are in line with observed
838 trends in underweight, overweight, and obesity ⁹.

839

840

841

842

843

844 **Table S1.** Overview of estimated dietary intake in 2020 by food category, food group, and
845 income region in grams per person per day (g/d) and kilocalories per person per day
846 (kcal/d). The category of processed foods converts some of the previously listed foods into
847 whether they are processed or not and are therefore not included in the total sum. All food
848 groups except processed foods refer to primary commodity equivalents (e.g., the amount of
849 milk or sugar contained in all unprocessed and processed foods).

Food category	Food group	Global		High income		Upper middle		Lower middle		Low income	
		(g/d)	(kcal/d)	(g/d)	(kcal/d)	(g/d)	(kcal/d)	(g/d)	(kcal/d)	(g/d)	(kcal/d)
staples	wheat	116	345	130	372	118	353	117	353	71	216
	rice	179	440	48	131	208	514	224	537	85	217
	maize	32	99	15	40	29	89	35	107	68	223
	other grains	19	57	12	30	7	19	21	62	89	271
	roots	132	112	95	64	115	93	129	110	306	312
fruits&veg	vegetables	256	66	174	46	388	94	183	50	142	54
	tropical fruits	41	20	46	21	54	21	31	22	17	8
	temperate fruits	68	32	71	43	90	40	53	23	33	17
	starchy fruits	30	21	18	11	24	15	33	23	68	55
legumes	legumes	19	65	10	33	10	33	27	94	39	135
	soybeans	4	14	4	14	7	26	1	3	1	4
nuts&seeds	nuts	11	39	13	51	12	42	9	33	9	33
	seeds	1	5	1	5	1	3	1	4	3	13
oils	vegetable oil	22	210	44	453	23	209	15	140	9	80
	palm and coconut	7	67	3	34	9	82	6	62	9	83
	fish oil	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
sugar	sugar	46	149	71	231	44	138	43	139	26	85
dairy	milk	172	130	394	271	138	98	133	120	75	57
	butter	4	30	8	56	1	10	5	44	0	3
	cream	1	2	6	11	1	1	0	0	0	0
eggs	eggs	25	36	33	47	42	61	10	14	3	4
seafood	freshwater fish	12	9	5	3	14	10	13	9	16	11
	pelagic fish	5	5	7	8	3	3	5	4	7	6
	demersal fish	4	2	8	7	4	2	2	1	2	1
	other fish	5	3	3	2	10	4	2	2	3	2
	shellfish	6	2	9	4	11	3	2	1	1	0
red meat	beef	17	26	35	42	20	33	8	13	10	18
	lamb	4	7	3	7	5	10	3	5	6	12
	pork	24	68	48	102	38	120	5	15	3	11
other meat	poultry	28	39	59	82	37	55	10	13	6	8
	other meat	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	2	2
animal fat	lard	2	24	3	54	3	30	1	9	1	9
other food	stimulants	3	4	6	13	3	4	2	2	2	2
	spices	3	8	1	5	1	4	4	14	3	8
	alcohol	52	36	119	75	61	45	19	14	40	20
	other	2	1	6	3	1	1	1	1	2	1
processed foods	whole grains	49	134	35	98	24	66	78	210	53	165
	processed grains	298	807	169	475	339	909	318	850	260	762
	red meat	35	81	55	94	54	144	11	24	12	25
	processed meat	11	21	32	57	9	19	4	9	8	16
	yoghurt	3	2	17	12	1	1	0	0	0	0
	cheese	8	27	40	136	3	11	1	3	2	5
	milk (actual)	129	101	177	123	120	86	129	117	70	52
total	all foods	2,176		2,375		2,270		2,044		1,981	

850

851 **S2 Nutritional assessment**

852

853 We estimated nutrient intake and adequacy by combining estimates of food intake with
854 nutrient densities and requirements. We used several sources of nutrient densities and
855 matched them to the level of food groups used for defining the dietary patterns. For most
856 food groups and nutrients, we relied on estimates provided by the Global Expanded Nutrient
857 Supply (GENuS) model. GENuS includes nutrient availabilities for 23 individual nutrients
858 across 225 food categories and all countries²¹. To obtain nutrient densities, we divided
859 national-level nutrient availabilities by matched intake values and then aggregated the
860 densities to the more general list of foods used in our analysis. We supplemented the data
861 by estimates from the Harvard Nutrient Database for missing nutrients (pantothenate and
862 vitamin B12) and selected foods and groups (whole grains, coloured vegetables, and
863 soybeans) not comprehensively covered by GENuS. In addition, we adopted iodine densities
864 of foods from the USDA nutrient database²², phytate densities from a dedicated and
865 standardised food composition table²³, and nutrient densities of algae from the latest edition
866 of the Japanese food composition table²⁴.

867

868 For comparing nutrient intake to requirements, we used a set of harmonised nutrient
869 reference values that specify the average nutrient requirements of populations by age and
870 sex²⁵. The estimates draw primarily from reference values developed by the European Food
871 Safety Authority (EFSA) and the National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and
872 Medicine of the USA (NASEM), giving priority to whichever values were developed more
873 recently. Estimated average requirements are generally provided for a specific reference
874 population (Europe for EFSA and the USA for NASEM). For our global analysis, we adapted
875 the estimated average requirements to other populations by adjusting the reference weights
876 used by the different institutes to the average body weights of the populations of interest. We
877 used isometric (linear) scaling or allometric (non-linear) scaling depending on the nutrient,
878 following the recommendations provided by the institutes from which the initial reference
879 value originated. We harmonised all age and sex estimates to the age and sex groups used
880 in our analysis and, in addition, calculated population averages by weighing each
881 demographic group by its population (including pregnant and lactating women, as well as
882 infants).

883

884 We accounted for changes in the bioavailability of zinc and iron modulated by food intake.
885 For zinc, we used the equations developed by Miller and colleagues²⁶ with updated
886 parameter values from Hambidge and colleagues²⁷ that describe zinc absorption dependent

887 on phytate concentrations. For iron, we separately accounted for heme and non-heme
888 absorption. For non-heme absorption, we used the equations developed by Armah and
889 colleagues²⁸ that describe absorption dependent on the dietary content of non-heme,
890 phytate, vitamin C, calcium, meat, tea, and serum ferritin levels.

891

892 We calculated the intake of and changes in nutrients across the different diets and
893 population groups for 26 nutrients. For nutrients for which adequacy-related average
894 requirements were available, we also calculated nutrient adequacy ratios (NARs) as the ratio
895 between estimated intake and recommended intake capped at one, and summed those
896 across nutrients to derive an overall adequacy scores (mean adequacy ratio, MAR) for each
897 population²⁹. We omitted nutrients in this calculation whose recommended intake were
898 based on balance studies and customary intake instead of requirements to avoid deficiency
899^{30,31}. Table S2 provides an overview of the nutrients included, their current average intake,
900 and their estimated average requirement related to adequacy where available.

901

902

903

904 **Table S2.** Overview of recommend intake and current intake of nutrients included in the
 905 analysis.

Nutrient	Unit	Recommended intake	Current intake
calories	kcal	2092.05	2230.19
protein	g	38	69.26
carbohydrates	g		323.33
fiber	g		25.1
fat	g		77.17
saturatedFA	g		26.33
monounsatFA	g		30.08
polyunsatFA	g		18.13
cholesterol	mg		180.23
calcium	mg		670.85
iron*	mg	absorption-dependent	16.95
magnesium	mg		392.64
phosphorus	mg	625.33	1247.75
potassium	mg		2600.35
zinc*	mg	absorption-dependent	10.64
copper	mg		1.59
iodine	mcg	91.75	166.64
vitaminC	mg	76.6	94.28
thiamin	mg	0.63	1.28
riboflavin	mg	1.22	0.99
niacin	mg	11.52	16.92
pantothenate	mg		6.34
vitaminB6	mg	1.3	4.06
folate	mcg	232.78	288.59
vitaminB12	mcg	1.85	3.14
vitaminA	mcg RAE	501.06	575.09

Notes: Recommended intake of iron and zinc (*) depends on absorption. The reported values of current intake refer to dietary intake, unadjusted for absorption.

906

907

908

909 **S3 Comparative risk assessment**

910

911 We estimated the mortality and disease burden attributable to dietary and weight-related risk
912 factors by calculating population impact fractions (PIFs) which represent the proportions of
913 disease cases that would be avoided when the risk exposure was changed from a baseline
914 situation to a counterfactual situation. For calculating PIFs, we used the general formula³²⁻³⁴:
915

$$PIF = \frac{\int RR(x)P(x)dx - \int RR(x)P'(x)dx}{\int RR(x)P(x)dx}$$

916

917 where $RR(x)$ is the relative risk of disease for risk factor level x , $P(x)$ is the number of
918 people in the population with risk factor level x in the baseline scenario, and $P'(x)$ is the
919 number of people in the population with risk factor level x in the counterfactual scenario. We
920 assumed that changes in relative risks follow a dose-response relationship,³³ and that PIFs
921 combine multiplicatively, i.e. $PIF = 1 - \prod_i(1 - PIF_i)$ where the i 's denote independent risk
922 factors.^{33,35}

923

924 The number of avoided deaths due to the change in risk exposure of risk i , $\Delta deaths_i$, was
925 calculated by multiplying the associated PIF by disease-specific death rates, DR , and by the
926 number of people alive within a population, P :

927

$$\Delta deaths_i(r, s, a, d) = PIF_i(r, s, a, d) \cdot DR(r, s, a, d) \cdot P(r, s, a)$$

928 where PIFs are differentiated by region r , sex s , age group a , and disease/cause of death d ;
929 the death rates are differentiated by region, sex, age group, and disease; the population
930 groups are differentiated by region, sex, and age group; and the change in the number of
931 deaths is differentiated by region, sex, age group, and disease.

932

933 We used publicly available data sources to parameterize the comparative risk analysis.
934 Mortality and population data were adopted from the Global Burden of Disease project.³⁶
935 Baseline data on the weight distribution in each country were adopted from a pooled
936 analysis of population-based measurements undertaken by the NCD Risk Factor
937 Collaboration.³⁷

938

939 The relative risk estimates that relate the risk factors to the disease endpoints were adopted
940 from meta-analyses of prospective cohort studies for dietary and weight-related risks.³⁸⁻⁴⁴ In
941 line with the meta-analyses, we included non-linear dose-response relationships for fruits,

942 vegetables, and nuts and seeds, and assumed linear dose-response relationships for the
 943 remaining risk factors. As our analysis was primarily focused on mortality from chronic
 944 diseases, we focused on adults aged 20 year or older, and we adjusted the relative-risk
 945 estimates for attenuation with age based on a pooled analysis of cohort studies focussed on
 946 metabolic risk factors,⁴⁵ in line with other assessments.^{34,46} Table S3 provides an overview of
 947 the relative-risk parameters used.

948

949 **Table S3.** Relative risk parameters (mean and low and high values of 95% confidence
 950 intervals) for dietary risks and weight-related risks.

Food group	Endpoint	Unit	RR mean	RR low	RR high	Reference
Processed meat	CHD	50 g/d	1.27	1.09	1.49	Bechthold et al (2019)
	Stroke	50 g/d	1.17	1.02	1.34	Bechthold et al (2019)
	Colorectal cancer	50 g/d	1.17	1.10	1.23	Schwingshackl et al (2018)
	Type 2 diabetes	50 g/d	1.37	1.22	1.55	Schwingshackl et al (2017)
Red meat	CHD	100 g/d	1.15	1.08	1.23	Bechthold et al (2019)
	Stroke	100 g/d	1.12	1.06	1.17	Bechthold et al (2019)
	Colorectal cancer	100 g/d	1.12	1.06	1.19	Schwingshackl et al (2018)
	Type 2 diabetes	100 g/d	1.17	1.08	1.26	Schwingshackl et al (2017)
Fruits	CHD	100 g/d	0.95	0.92	0.99	Aune et al (2017)
	Stroke	100 g/d	0.77	0.70	0.84	Aune et al (2017)
	Cancer	100 g/d	0.94	0.91	0.97	Aune et al (2017)
Vegetables	CHD	100 g/d	0.84	0.80	0.88	Aune et al (2017)
	Cancer	100 g/d	0.93	0.91	0.95	Aune et al (2017)
Legumes	CHD	57 g/d	0.86	0.78	0.94	Afshin et al (2014)
Nuts	CHD	28 g/d	0.71	0.63	0.80	Aune et al (2016)
Whole grains	CHD	30 g/d	0.87	0.85	0.90	Aune et al (2016b)
	Cancer	30 g/d	0.95	0.93	0.97	Aune et al (2016b)
	Type 2 diabetes	30 g/d	0.65	0.61	0.70	Aune et al (2016b)
Underweight	CHD	15<BMI<18.5	1.17	1.09	1.24	Global BMI Collab (2016)
	Stroke	15<BMI<18.5	1.37	1.23	1.53	Global BMI Collab (2016)
	Cancer	15<BMI<18.5	1.10	1.05	1.16	Global BMI Collab (2016)
	Respiratory disease	15<BMI<18.5	2.73	2.31	3.23	Global BMI Collab (2016)
Overweight	CHD	25<BMI<30	1.34	1.32	1.35	Global BMI Collab (2016)
	Stroke	25<BMI<30	1.11	1.09	1.14	Global BMI Collab (2016)
	Cancer	25<BMI<30	1.10	1.09	1.12	Global BMI Collab (2016)
	Respiratory disease	25<BMI<30	0.90	0.87	0.94	Global BMI Collab (2016)
	Type 2 diabetes	25<BMI<30	1.88	1.56	2.11	Prosp Studies Collab (2009)
Obesity (grade 1)	CHD	30<BMI<35	2.02	1.91	2.13	Global BMI Collab (2016)
	Stroke	30<BMI<35	1.46	1.39	1.54	Global BMI Collab (2016)
	Cancer	30<BMI<35	1.31	1.28	1.34	Global BMI Collab (2016)
	Respiratory disease	30<BMI<35	1.16	1.08	1.24	Global BMI Collab (2016)
	Type 2 diabetes	30<BMI<35	3.53	2.43	4.45	Prosp Studies Collab (2009)
Obesity (grade 2)	CHD	30<BMI<35	2.81	2.63	3.01	Global BMI Collab (2016)
	Stroke	30<BMI<35	2.11	1.93	2.30	Global BMI Collab (2016)
	Cancer	30<BMI<35	1.57	1.50	1.63	Global BMI Collab (2016)
	Respiratory disease	30<BMI<35	1.79	1.60	1.99	Global BMI Collab (2016)
	Type 2 diabetes	30<BMI<35	6.64	3.80	9.39	Prosp Studies Collab (2009)
Obesity (grade 3)	CHD	30<BMI<35	3.81	3.47	4.17	Global BMI Collab (2016)
	Stroke	30<BMI<35	2.33	2.05	2.65	Global BMI Collab (2016)
	Cancer	30<BMI<35	1.96	1.83	2.09	Global BMI Collab (2016)
	Respiratory disease	30<BMI<35	2.85	2.43	3.34	Global BMI Collab (2016)
	Type 2 diabetes	30<BMI<35	12.49	5.92	19.82	Prosp Studies Collab (2009)

951

952 The selection of risk-disease associations used in the health analysis was supported by
 953 available criteria used to judge the certainty of evidence, such as the Bradford-Hill criteria
 954 used by the Nutrition and Chronic Diseases Expert Group (NutriCoDE),⁴⁶ the World-Cancer-
 955 Research-Fund criteria used by the Global Burden of Disease project,⁴⁷ as well as
 956 NutriGrade (Table S4).⁴⁸ The certainty of evidence supporting the associations of dietary
 957 risks and disease outcomes as used here were graded as moderate or high with
 958 NutriGrade,^{41–43} and/or assessed as probable or convincing by the Nutrition and Chronic
 959 Diseases Expert Group,⁴⁶ and by the World Cancer Research.⁴⁹ The certainty of evidence
 960 grading in each case relates to the general relationship between a risk factor and a health
 961 outcome, and not to a specific relative-risk value.

962

963 **Table S4.** Overview of existing ratings on the certainty of evidence for a statistically
 964 significant association between a risk factor and a disease endpoint. The ratings include
 965 those of the Nutrition and Chronic Diseases Expert Group (NutriCoDE),⁴⁶ the World Cancer
 966 Research Fund,⁴⁹ and NutriGrade.^{41–43} The ratings relate to the risk-disease associations in
 967 general, and not to the specific relative-risk factor used for those associations in this
 968 analysis.

Food group	Endpoint	Association	Certainty of evidence
Fruits	CHD	reduction	NutriCoDE: probable or convincing; NutriGrade: moderate quality of meta-evidence
	Stroke	reduction	NutriCoDE: probable or convincing NutriGrade: moderate quality of meta-evidence
	Cancer	reduction	WCRF: strong evidence (probable) for some cancers NutriGrade: moderate quality of meta-evidence for colorectal cancer
Vegetables	CHD	reduction	NutriCoDE: probable or convincing NutriGrade: moderate quality of meta-evidence
	Cancer	reduction	WCRF: strong evidence (probable) for non-starchy vegetables and some cancers NutriGrade: moderate quality of meta-evidence for colorectal cancer
Legumes	CHD	reduction	NutriCoDE: probable or convincing NutriGrade: moderate quality of meta-evidence
Nuts and seeds	CHD	reduction	NutriCoDE: probable or convincing NutriGrade: moderate quality of meta-evidence
Whole grains	CHD	reduction	NutriCoDE: probable or convincing NutriGrade: moderate quality of meta-evidence
	Cancer	reduction	WCRF: strong evidence (probable) for colorectal cancer NutriGrade: moderate quality of meta-evidence for colorectal cancer
	Type-2 diabetes	reduction	NutriCoDE: probable or convincing NutriGrade: high quality of meta-evidence
Red meat	CHD	increase	NutriGrade: moderate quality of meta-evidence
	Stroke	increase	NutriGrade: moderate quality of meta-evidence
	Cancer	increase	WCRF: strong evidence (probable) for colorectal cancer NutriGrade: moderate quality of meta-evidence for colorectal cancer
	Type-2 diabetes	increase	NutriCoDE: probable or convincing NutriGrade: high quality of meta-evidence
Processed meat	CHD	increase	NutriCoDE: probable or convincing NutriGrade: moderate quality of meta-evidence
	Stroke	increase	NutriGrade: moderate quality of meta-evidence
	Cancer	increase	WCRF: strong evidence (convincing) for colorectal cancer NutriGrade: moderate quality of meta-evidence for colorectal cancer
	Type-2 diabetes	increase	NutriGrade: high quality of meta-evidence

NutriCoDE: Nutrition and Chronic Diseases Expert Group

NutriGrade: Grading of Recommendations Assessment, Development, and Evaluation (GRADE) tailored to nutrition research

WCRF: World Cancer Research Fund

969

970 We did not include all available risk-disease associations that were graded as having a
971 moderate certainty of evidence and showed statistically significant results in the meta-
972 analyses that included NutriGrade assessments.⁴¹⁻⁴³ That was because for some
973 associations, such as for milk and fish, more detailed meta-analyses (with more sensitivity
974 analyses) were available that indicated potential confounding with other major dietary risks
975 or health status at baseline.⁵⁰⁻⁵² Such sensitivity analyses were not presented in the meta-
976 analyses that included NutriGrade assessments, but they are important for health
977 assessments that evaluate changes in multiple risk factors.

978

979 For each risk factor, we constrained the maximum attainable risk reduction to minimal risk
980 exposure values established by NutriCoDe and available meta-analyses^{38-43,46,53}. They
981 included 300 g/d for fruits, 500 g/d for vegetables, 100 g/d for legumes, 20 g/d for nuts, 125
982 g/d for whole grains, and 0 g/d for red meat and processed meat. For a sensitivity analysis,
983 we also attributed the burden of weight-related risks to the under and overconsumption of
984 foods and the associated calorie imbalances. We used the reference values for healthy
985 eating (Fig 1A) as implemented in the set of healthy and sustainable dietary patterns the
986 comparator for that analysis. We used the calorie distribution across underconsumed
987 (encouraged) foods to attribute the burden of underweight, and the distribution across
988 overconsumed (discouraged) foods to attribute to burden of overweight and obesity.

989

990 For the different diet scenarios, we calculated uncertainty intervals associated with changes
991 in mortality based on standard methods of error propagation and the confidence intervals of
992 the relative risk parameters. For the error propagation, we approximated the error
993 distribution of the relative risks by a normal distribution and used that side of deviations from
994 the mean which was largest. This method leads to conservative and potentially larger
995 uncertainty intervals as probabilistic methods, such as Monte Carlo sampling, but it has
996 significant computational advantages, and is justified for the magnitude of errors dealt with
997 here (<50%) (see e.g. IPCC Uncertainty Guidelines).

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1007 **S4 Environmental assessment**

1008

1009 For the estimating food-related environmental impacts, we converted the estimates of food
 1010 intake to total food demand, and then paired those with a set of trade-adjusted and
 1011 regionalised environmental footprints⁵⁴. Table S5 provides an overview of the footprints
 1012 used and their food-related detail. The main methods section explains how we converted
 1013 food intake to food demand and provides further details on how the environmental footprints
 1014 were derived.

1015

1016 **Table S5.** Overview of environmental footprints per kg of product.

Food group	GHG emission (ktCO ₂ eq)	Land use (km ²)	Freshwater use (km ³)	Eutrophication potential (ktPO ₄ ³⁻ eq)
wheat	1.19	2.54	585.96	5.04
rice	3.39	1.94	2070.04	8.85
maize	0.72	1.08	125.33	1.45
other grains	1.00	2.01	353.03	3.45
roots	0.55	0.79	31.48	2.63
vegetables	0.42	0.19	107.92	1.92
fruits (tropical)	0.51	0.64	108.30	1.48
fruits (temperate)	0.61	0.75	149.80	1.54
fruits (starchy)	0.72	0.87	100.26	2.09
legumes	1.26	10.58	375.39	11.14
soybeans	1.27	1.19	54.23	2.35
nuts	0.60	4.91	1797.69	9.34
seeds	0.95	1.81	355.65	3.25
vegetable oils	3.96	11.70	604.89	17.56
palm oil	7.51	2.42	6.58	10.56
sugar	2.28	1.24	410.71	7.68
beef	31.94	69.42	1284.11	156.99
lamb	26.48	80.72	1142.03	65.02
pork	6.46	8.38	1108.60	31.49
poultry	5.21	7.10	423.46	21.70
other meat	39.51	110.08	923.00	203.81
eggs	4.28	5.80	582.66	21.29
milk	2.46	2.03	547.62	9.90
animal fats	4.02	4.67	648.61	17.62
fish	1.11	0.76	449.97	33.72
shellfish	4.89	0.26	915.23	46.29
stimulants	3.29	10.08	134.52	21.80
other crops	1.26	1.29	32.19	2.76

1017 In addition to reporting changes in environmental impacts for each domain, we also
 1018 calculated an overall indicator of food-related environmental impacts for which we weighed
 1019 the changes in each domain by the needed contribution of dietary changes towards staying
 1020 within food-related environmental limits (or planetary boundaries), also considering other
 1021 food-system measures⁵⁵. The dietary contributions to mitigation in line with staying within
 1022 planetary boundaries amounted to 70% for GHG emissions, 18% for land use, 19% for water
 1023 use, 17% for nitrogen application, and 18% for phosphorus application (Figure S1).
 1024 Normalised to sum to 100% and assigning the contributions of diet-related reduction in
 1025 nitrogen and phosphorus application to eutrophication (which ecologically is related to both)
 1026 resulted in weighing fractions of 46% for GHG emissions, 12% each for land use and water
 1027 use, and 30% for eutrophication potential.

1028

1029 **Figure S1.** Contribution of mitigation measures to simultaneously reduce environmental
 1030 impacts below environmental limits (planetary boundaries); adapted from Springmann and
 1031 colleagues⁵⁵ (Figure 4). The mitigation measures include dietary changes to flexitarian diets
 1032 (FLX), technological improvements of medium (tech) and high ambition (tech+), halving of
 1033 food loss and waste (w/2), and socioeconomic development with higher income growth and
 1034 lower population growth (SSP1).

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1040 **S5 Supplementary results**

1041

1042 **Figure S2.** Regional variation in current energy intake (**A**), energy requirements associated
1043 with recommended body weights and physical activity levels (**B**), energy requirements
1044 associated with recommended body weights at current physical activity levels (**C**).

1045

1046

1047 **Figure S3.** Food intake by dietary pattern, and for the example of flexitarian diets by region,
 1048 age, and sex in terms of kilocalories per person per day (A), grams per person per day (B),
 1049 and servings per person per day (C). The dietary patterns include flexitarian (FLX),
 1050 pescatarian (PSC), vegetarian (VEG), and vegan (VGN) diets. The regions include North
 1051 America (NAC), Latin America & Caribbean (LCN), Europe & Central Asia (ECS), Middle
 1052 East & North Africa (MEA), South Asia (SAS), East Asia & Pacific (EAS), and Sub-Saharan
 1053 Africa (SSF).

1054
 1055

1056 **Figure S4.** Change in food intake by dietary pattern, and for the example of flexitarian diets
 1057 by region, age, and sex in terms of kilocalories per person per day (A), grams per person per
 1058 day (B), and servings per person per day (C). The dietary patterns include flexitarian (FLX),
 1059 pescatarian (PSC), vegetarian (VEG), and vegan (VGN) diets. The regions include North
 1060 America (NAC), Latin America & Caribbean (LCN), Europe & Central Asia (ECS), Middle
 1061 East & North Africa (MEA), South Asia (SAS), East Asia & Pacific (EAS), and Sub-Saharan
 1062 Africa (SSF).

1063
1064

1065 **Figure S5.** Change in food intake, including in processed foods, by dietary pattern, and for
 1066 the example of flexitarian diets by region, age, and sex in terms of kilocalories per person
 1067 per day (A), grams per person per day (B), and servings per person per day (C). The dietary
 1068 patterns include flexitarian (FLX), pescatarian (PSC), vegetarian (VEG), and vegan (VGN)
 1069 diets. The regions include North America (NAC), Latin America & Caribbean (LCN), Europe
 1070 & Central Asia (ECS), Middle East & North Africa (MEA), South Asia (SAS), East Asia &
 1071 Pacific (EAS), and Sub-Saharan Africa (SSF).

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1075 **Figure S6.** Overall change in food intake by food group and diet scenario (%), including
 1076 primary foods (A) and processed foods (B).

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1080 **Figure S7.** Overall percentage changes in the intake of encouraged foods with minimum
 1081 targets (min targets, **A**) and of to-be-limited foods with maximum targets (max targets, **A**) by
 1082 dietary pattern, and for the example of flexitarian diets also by region, age, and sex. Panel **B**
 1083 depicts the same overall changes, but with proportional contributions of each food to the
 1084 overall percentage change.

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 1086
 1087
 1088

1089 **Figure S8.** Overall percentage changes in the intake of encouraged (A) and to-be-limited (B)
1090 foods by country and for the example of flexitarian diets.

A

B

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1094 **Figure S9.** Globally averaged percentage changes in nutrient intake by nutrient and dietary
 1095 pattern.

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1098 **Figure S10.** Mean adequacy scores by region, age, and sex in the baseline and the dietary
 1099 patterns. The scores were calculated by summing nutritional adequacy ratios over nutrients
 1100 with adequacy-related recommendations and dividing by their number.

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1107 **Figure S11.** Regional distribution of mean adequacy ratios in the baseline (A) and the
1108 dietary patterns (B). Please note that mean adequacy scores of 100% at a country level are
1109 averages and do not indicate full adequacy of each population group.
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1115 **Figure S12.** Global reduction in mortality by risk factor and dietary pattern. Risk factors
 1116 include low intake of whole grains, vegetables, fruits, legumes, nuts and seeds; high intake
 1117 of red meat and processed meat; and imbalances in energy intake associated with
 1118 underweight, overweight, and obesity.

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1121 **Figure S13.** Reduction in mortality by dietary pattern, and for flexitarian diets also by region,
 1122 age group, and sex. Panel **A** displays the reduction in mortality attributed to changes in diet
 1123 and weight-related risk factors. Panel **B** displays the reduction in mortality with diet-related
 1124 risk factors as in panel **A** and with weight-related risk factors attributed the under and
 1125 overconsumption of foods (including to foods directly associated with diet-related risks).

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1134 **Figure S14.** Change in mortality by country and dietary pattern, including flexitarian (A),
1135 pescatarian (B), vegetarian (C), and vegan (D) diets.

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1138 **Figure S15.** Global reduction in environmental resource use and pollution by environmental
1139 indicator and dietary pattern.

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1144 **Figure S16.** Reduction in averaged environmental resource demand by dietary pattern, and
 1145 for flexitarian diets also by region, age group, and sex. The changes in environmental
 1146 impacts were averaged across domains (GHG emissions, land use, water use, and
 1147 eutrophication potential), weighted by the importance of dietary changes for mitigation in that
 1148 domain.

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1151 **Figure S17.** Reduction in environmental resource use and pollution by dietary pattern, and
 1152 for flexitarian diets also by region, age group, and sex across environmental domains,
 1153 including GHG emissions (A), land use (B), water use (C), and eutrophication potential (D).

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1156 **Figure 18.** Change in averaged environmental impacts by country and dietary pattern,
1157 including flexitarian (A), pescatarian (B), vegetarian (C), and vegan (D) diets.

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1161 **Figure S19.** Sensitivity analysis of different ways of developing planetary health diets. The
 1162 sensitivity analysis compares four ways of developing the dietary patterns **(A)** and the
 1163 associated impacts on mortality by risk factor **(B)** and environmental resource demand by
 1164 food group **(C)**. They include the main variants which regionalise dietary recommendations
 1165 without penalising greater than recommended intake of encouraged foods and lower than
 1166 recommended intake of to-be-limited foods (*main*), static variants with strict adherence to the
 1167 dietary reference values (*static*), variants that are regionalised as the main and adapted to
 1168 the energy requirements of populations that meet recommended levels of physical activity
 1169 (*active*), and variants that include static adherence to the reference values and illustrate the
 1170 impacts of misapplying the energy requirements of one population group with energy
 1171 requirements of 2500 kcal/d to all other groups (*adult*).

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